

**Corrosion Inhibition Studies by
Electrodeposition and Inhibitors**

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Since centuries man has been using metals for one or the other purposes to suit his needs. In the course of time he developed improvised technology for retrieving metal, fabrication technology for shaping metals to articles of his desire. The very form from which metal was won indicate the stablest state it would like to have incase left alone or in other words metal goes back to its combined form. This process of loosing metal is referred as corrosion phenomena.

The corrosion of metals received a prime attention of material scientists and chemists since it has many serious consequences including economic, health, safety, technological and cultural consequences all over the world. If economic loss alone is considered, the costs associated with corrosion losses can be estimated with reasonable accuracy. The typical estimations were US \$275 billion dollars in 1998, US\$364 billion dollars in 2005, draining about 3.1% of the GDP from the US economy. These numbers alone justify much greater need for development of newer corrosion protection techniques.

Large number of methods is available in literature for corrosion protection. Among these methods, electroplating, corrosion inhibition and surface modification are largely adopted.

Electroplating, use of corrosion inhibition and surface modification methods are adopted for controlling corrosion rate depending on the nature of its end use. The corrosion control in all these methods follows altogether different mechanism. In an electroplating the entire base metal (steel) is covered with zinc (thick) coating which is generated by electrolysis of aqueous solution containing zinc salt, conducting salt and organic additives. These additives are specific in their action and produce shining, bright, uniform, monoporous adhered deposit and are considered as effective brighteners. Generally bright zinc deposit are superior to dull zinc coating and provide better corrosion protection as well an aesthetic appeal. However in some aggressive environment this deposit fails to do its function. An alternative to this is the alloy deposition of zinc with iron group metals has considered. The alloy deposition can give certain higher degree of protection but its application is limited due to its failure to

generate alloy deposit of desired composition. Also during service the alloy coating may exhibit galvanic corrosion. However better corrosion resistance property of bright Zn-Fe alloy deposits have been reported in the recent literature.

As a consequence of the above difficulties the efforts have been put to generate coating possessing higher corrosion resistance property during deposition itself [22-26]. This is achieved by incorporating certain inert micro sized particles in the deposit during deposition process of the zinc.

The mechanical incorporation of inert particles is done by electrolyzing an aqueous solution containing uniformly distributed micro particles. Such deposit possesses better chemical, physical, mechanical, corrosion resistance properties. There are few reports in literature on the zinc coating with certain micro sized particles for certain functional properties but no report on the use of nano sized particles on resistance property of zinc deposit. The present work has been undertaken to investigate the use of nano sized particles as addition agents on electrodeposition of zinc. Its inclusion in the deposit along with its contribution to enhance the corrosion resistance property of zinc deposit. The composite coating property is explored by adopting regular chemical, electrochemical and industrial tests.

The corrosion inhibition method is employed in a situation where the entire surface of composite coating or zinc metal immersed in aggressive media. The addition agents (organic compounds) are added to corrosive media to inhibit the rate of either cathodic or anodic reactions and by doing so the corrosion process of metal is controlled. These addition agents are referred as corrosion inhibitors. Even though this method is one of the oldest and much work has been carried out to find out effective, efficient, toxic free corrosion inhibitors. Still there is demand for corrosion inhibitors which will have higher inhibition efficiency than existing ones. In the present work effort has been done in developing good corrosion inhibition for zinc and steel

The other method in great demand is chemical surface modification of metal by organic addition agents against its corrosion [28-29]. It is a new approach and possesses little past history and very little citation in the literature. In the present study the focus has been given to investigate good zinc surface modifiers.

The present thesis comprises the results of all the above three methods and represented systematically in fourteen chapters.

Chapter One: This chapter contains two parts. Part A deals with the general and basic aspects of electrodeposition, role of addition agents in electrodeposition, mechanism of electrodeposition in presence of different addition agents. Also given different techniques used to study the performance of coatings. Finally literature survey on zinc composite coatings has been given.

Part B deals with the basic aspects of corrosion, consequences of corrosion and types of corrosion, types of inhibitors, factors which influence inhibition action and its mechanism. Also discussed the literature aspects used to study the role of inhibitors and surface modifiers

Chapter Two deals with the aim and scope of the work and also highlights the importance of the present investigation.

In the Third Chapter, Zn-Ni-CNT composite coating from sulphate bath was discussed and also concentration of CNTs in the bath was optimized. These coatings were characterized by SEM and XRD. Finally, corrosion studies of the coatings were studied.

In Fourth Chapter, Zn-carbon black composite coating and its corrosion behavior was studied. Coatings were characterized by SEM. All these coatings corrosion studies were discussed in this chapter.

In the Fifth Chapter, Zn-Fe bright coating was developed by using new brightener formed by the Vertraldehyde and Serine Schiff base. Hull cell used to optimize the current density. These deposits are pore-free and corrosion resistant.

In the Sixth Chapter, Zn – Ni bright coating was developed by newly synthesized condensation product between Vanillin and Chitosan. The brightener was easily soluble in water. Hence the deposit is pore-free and corrosion resistant. Brightener effect on bright coating was characterized.

In Seventh Chapter, Corrosion inhibition studies were carried out for steel and zinc by using Metol as an Inhibitor. Chemical and Electrochemical methods were used to study the corrosion behavior of the inhibitor.

In Eighth Chapter, BMP and MMDP compounds were shown as an inhibitor for zinc by surface modification method. Detailed mechanism of the inhibition was explained in this chapter.

In Ninth Chapter, Olmesartan was developed as corrosion inhibitor for steel by theoretical and Experimental methods. Quantum studies and molecular dynamics were used calculate the inhibition efficiency of the inhibitor. Finally, electrochemical methods, activation parameters and thermodynamic parameters were used to study the corrosion mechanism.

In Tenth Chapter, discussed about Praziquantel as corrosion inhibitor. Praziquantel acts as an active corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 1M HCl solution. Thermodynamic parameters, activation parameters and electrochemical methods were used to study the corrosion inhibition.

In Eleventh Chapter, studied about Sulfamethoxazole as an inhibitor. Thermodynamic parameters, activation parameters and electrochemical methods were used to study the corrosion inhibition.

In Twelfth Chapter, Tert-butyl 4-[(4-methylphenyl) carbonyl] piperazine-1-carboxylate (TBMPCPC) was developed as an inhibitor. Developed inhibitor was characterized. These molecules were used as effective inhibitor.

In Thirteen Chapter, discussed about Telmisartan as an inhibitor for steel. Thermodynamic parameters, Activation parameters and Electrochemical methods were used to study the corrosion inhibition.

Finally, in Fourteenth Chapter concluded with overall work of the thesis.